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DeepRIoT: Continuous Integration and Deployment Of Robotic-IoT Applications

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Motivation

- **Sample Inefficiency:** Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) requires a vast amount of sample data from interactions with the environment, which is highly impractical in real-world settings due to time, safety and cost constraints.
- **Generalization Issues:** a RL model trained in a specific environment may not perform well in slightly different settings.
- **Simulation-to-Reality Gap:** the discrepancy between simulated environments and real-world conditions poses a challenge that models trained in simulation often do not transfer well to real-world scenarios.

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Contribution

- **DeepRIoT framework - systematic approach that accelerates learning and deployment of RL model on real robotic-IoT system.**
- Sim2Real solution - optimize plant model via supervised learning (SL) and use transfer learning (TL) to adapt model from controlled settings to practical applications.
- CI/CD integration - automates DeepRIoT framework.

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DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

- Task Specification Φ

- Motion planning

- Reachability

$$\Phi_R = G(s_0 \wedge \theta_0 \rightarrow F (|x - x_g| < \epsilon \wedge (|y - y_g| < \epsilon)))$$

- Safety

$$\Phi_S = G(d_{s,min} > d_0)$$

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

- Simulation of Environment
 - *f1tenth_gym* [1] - F1TENTH autonomous racing platform

[1] Matthew O'Kelly et al. F1TENTH: an open-source evaluation environment for continuous control and reinforcement learning. In NeurIPS 2019 Competition and Demonstration Track, volume 123, pages 77–89. PMLR, 2019.

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

• Robot Model

• Kinematics (KiModel)

- ~~X~~ force
- simpler, less computationally intensive
- basic motion planning and control

• Dynamics (DyModel)

- \checkmark force
- more complex, more computationally intensive
- necessary for precise control

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

- **RL Training Environment**

- Observation space O_t

$$O_{1t} = [\Delta x_t, \Delta y_t, \theta_t, v_{bx_t}, \omega_t]$$

$$O_{2t} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1080}$$

$$O_t = [O_{1t}, O_{2t}]$$

O_{1t} - relative pos, heading angle, longitudinal vel, angular vel

O_{2t} - last three consecutive frames of laser scans (1080 beams)

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

- **RL Training Environment**

- Action space A_t

$$A_t = [\delta_t^*, v_{bx_t}^*]$$

A_t - desired steering angle, desired longitudinal velocity

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

• RL Training Environment

• Reward function R_t

- *Distance reward*

$$r_d(t) = -(|\Delta x_t| + |\Delta y_t|)^{1/2}$$

- *Distance-change reward*

$$r_{dc}(t) = -\tanh[\Delta d_t \cdot \gamma_1] \cdot w_1$$

- *Angle-change reward*

$$r_{ac}(t) = \begin{cases} |h_{t-1}| - |h_t|, & \text{towards target} \\ -10, & \text{off target} \end{cases}$$

- *Collision-distance reward*

$$r_{cd}(t) = 400 - 40 / (0.05 \cdot \bar{d}_t + 0.25)$$

- *Collision-rate reward*

$$r_{cr}(t) = \tanh(\Delta \bar{d}_t \cdot \gamma_2) \cdot w_2$$

DeepRloT: A - Application initiation

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DeepRIoT: B - Feature engineering

- **Observer and Filter**

- Gaussian noises added to LiDAR scan
- Butterworth - high-frequency actions filter to protect motor

DeepRIoT: C - Policy training (RL)

• Neural Network Design

DeepRIoT: C - Policy training (RL)

Neural Network Design

DeepRIoT: C - Policy training (RL)

• Training Procedure

- Block-wise random initialization
- Symbolic abstraction
 - T_1 - collision danger \times , towards target \checkmark
 - T_2 - collision danger \times , towards target \times
 - T_3 - collision danger \checkmark
- Dynamic allocation of replay buffer
 - Experiences (s, a, r, s') stored in replay buffers
 - RB_i stores experiences from T_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$)

DeepRIoT: C - Policy training (RL)

• Training Procedure

• Multi-stage training

- S_1 - encourage car to reach the target
- S_2 - focus on collision avoidance
- S_3 - converge quickly when car approaches to the target

DeepRIoT: C - Policy training (RL)

- Policy Export

- Base policy (trained on *KiModel*) exported to policy repository after learning curve converged

DeepRloT: D- Model training (SL)

• Policy Evaluation

- **Success rate** - percentage of satisfying Φ among training episodes
- Test trained policy on dynamic model (DyModel)
 - Passed \checkmark - E. Sim2Real
 - Failed \times - Plant model training

DeepRIoT: D- Model training (SL)

• Plant model training (SL)

• Dynamic model (DyModel)

$$\begin{cases} ma_{by} = F_{rby} + F_{fby} \\ I_z \ddot{\psi} = -l_r F_{rby} + l_f F_{fby} \end{cases}$$

F_f and F_{rby} provide a positive moment M_{bz} that finally makes the car turn left and deviate the velocity at $G(v_g)$ from the wheelbase by a slip angle β .

DeepRIoT: D- Model training (SL)

Plant model training (SL)

Kinematic model (KiModel)

$$\psi = v_g \tan \delta / (l_f + l_r)$$

KiModel assumes no slip angle β and considers no frictions. Heading angle ψ is changed according to the car's geometric relation with steering angle δ .

DeepRloT: D- Model training (SL)

- Plant model training (SL)

- Model optimization workflow

- State-space form: $\dot{x} = Ax + Bu$

- Matrices A and B : contain constant parameters P that defines the system dynamics (base model)

- Optimization goal: optimize the parameters P with SL, by using traces (labels) from the target model to obtain P'

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DeepRIoT: D- Model training (SL)

- Plant model training (SL)
- **Model adaptation** - use transfer learning to make the policy (P) adapt to updated params P' (return to C. Policy training)

DeepRIoT: E- Sim2Real

- **Sim2Real**

- **Mixed-reality settings** - virtual car and real car can **percept** each other and reach their goal positions without collision
- Evaluate the performance of policy (trained on *DyModel*) deployed on real F1TENTH car
 - Passed ✓ - Termination
 - Failed ✗ - Plant model training

DeepRIoT: E- Sim2Real

• Sim2Real

- **Mixed-reality settings** - virtual car and real car can **percept** each other and reach their goal positions without collision
- Evaluate the performance of policy (trained on *DyModel*) deployed on mixed-reality:
 - Passed \checkmark - Termination
 - Failed \times - Plant model training

DeepRIoT: E- Sim2Real

- **Sim2Real**

- Plant model training & Model adaptation - same approach as mentioned in D. Model training

Experiment - Hardware and Software Settings

• Hardware and Software Architecture

- Cloud Layer
 - CI/CD integration
 - Machine Learning
- Edge Layer
 - ROS2 middleware
- Sensor Layer
 - F1TENTH car

Figure 1: Hardware and Software Architecture

Experiment - Training Results

(A) Average rewards

(B) Steps

Figure 2: Comparison between w/wo model training

Experiment - Policy Evaluation

(A) Trajectory Heatmap

(B) Situation Distribution

Figure 3: Policy evaluation in simulation

Experiment - Deployment

(A) Heatmap

(B) Simulation

(C) Deployment

Figure 4: The deployment of trained policy

THE CHIPS TO SYSTEMS CONFERENCE

SHAPING THE NEXT GENERATION OF ELECTRONICS

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Thank you for your listening!

